

Exploring 17th Century Formosa: The Dutch Colonial Period (1624-1662)

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 21 July 2025</p>	<p>Formosa (Taiwan), due to its unique geographical location, became a key contested area for Western maritime powers during the Age of Exploration. During the 38 years of Dutch East India Company (VOC) colonization in western Taiwan, it is evident that the primary focus was on economic interests, with the secondary goal being the assimilation of the indigenous population. A large number of Han Chinese from the Fujian Minnan region were brought in, initiating the process of sinicization in Taiwan. (1) on assimilation: The Dutch used military force to facilitate missionary work, implementing policies of religious indoctrination, encouraging intermarriage, suppressing "shamanistic" beliefs, and rebuilding the social order and morality of the indigenous people. (2) on sovereignty: The Dutch established vassal relationships, annual tribute system, and taxation policies to ensure that both indigenous and Han populations recognized the legitimacy of Dutch rule, while also communicating to foreign nations that they held sovereignty over the western region of Taiwan. (3) on reasons for losing Formosa: The loss of Formosa can be attributed to internal conflicts within the VOC and the shifting geopolitical and military dynamics caused by the Ming-Qing transition in China.</p>
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1. INTRODUCTION: The Eve of Dutch Colonial Rule in Taiwan (Before 1624)

1.1 Western European Maritime Powers Sailed East in Pursuit of Wealth

Although the history of Western Europe may initially seem unrelated to Taiwan, it has had a profound impact on the island's historical development over the past four centuries. In January 1492, Spain completed the Reconquista by reclaiming the last Muslim-ruled kingdom, the Nasrid Kingdom of Granada, on the Iberian Peninsula. Subsequently, Spain and Portugal began sailing out of the Atlantic in search of new trade routes. That same year, after Christopher Columbus discovered the Americas, European nations—driven by both mercantile interests and religious fervor—emerged as new maritime powers. They set out to explore and colonize distant lands, aiming to establish trade routes, secure colonial territories, and strengthen their global economic influence.

Due to its unique geographical location, Taiwan became a highly contested territory among several Western European countries. The backdrop of this period was defined by the Age of Discovery, Mercantilism, and the rise of World Evangelism. The emerging maritime powers of Western Europe were actively expanding their naval influence and

seeking new trade routes in the East. Their ambitions involved not only maritime trade but also colonization and missionary efforts, all with the support of the Roman Catholic Church. Driven by national interests and military power, these countries sought to conquer, colonize, and convert the local populations, marking a historic turning point for the colonized peoples (Ormond, 2003).

1.2 Treat Penghu Island as the Second Macau

In 1553, the Portuguese gradually established colonial control over Macau through a leasing arrangement (Chen, 2018). They exploited Macau's strategic geographical position to engage in trade with the Ming Dynasty, monopolizing the trade of silk, porcelain, silver, and gold, while also controlling the maritime trade network. The substantial profits generated from this trade provoked jealousy from the Dutch East India Company (VOC). Other Western nations, attempting to penetrate the Ming Dynasty market, were unsuccessful and could only engage with smugglers and maritime traders (Fang, 2010).

The VOC aimed to establish trade outposts that could engage in commerce with both the Ming Dynasty and Japan, with the goal of breaking the maritime trade monopoly held by Portugal and Spain. As a result, they made several military attempts to attack Macau and, on two occasions (1604 and

1622), invaded Makung (馬公) in the Penghu Islands to set up trade posts. During the second invasion of the Penghu Islands in 1622, the VOC learned from captured Spanish vessels that Spain was preparing to occupy Dàyuan (大員) (present-day Anping in Tainan, Taiwan), which prompted the VOC's interest. In April of that year, the VOC dispatched ships from Batavia to first attack Macau, intending to seize the profitable port from the Portuguese and replace them as the dominant trading power with the Ming Dynasty and Japan. Alternatively, they planned to occupy the Penghu Islands, transforming it into a "second Macau," while also confirming Spain's intentions to seize the strategic location of Dàyuan (Vande Walle, 2015).

During the VOC's occupation of the Pescadores, they were completely driven out by the Ming Dynasty's Fujian navy (Lin, 2022). Eventually, the VOC requested the intervention of the maritime merchant Li Dan (李旦) to mediate the ceasefire. Li Dan then recommended Zheng Zhilong to serve as the interpreter for the mission (Andrade, 2008) and strongly advised the Dutch to withdraw from the Pescadores and relocate to Dàyuan. The Ming Dynasty agreed not to obstruct or intercept Dutch merchant ships trading in Dàyuan. Ultimately, after considering various factors, the new VOC governor, Martinus Sonck, reached an agreement with the Ming Dynasty, consenting to dismantle the Fengguiwei (風櫃尾) fortress and battery. As a result, the Dutch withdrew in August 1624 and relocated to Dàyuan.

From the VOC's view, Macau was the top choice, as it was the best trading post with the Ming Dynasty. The second choice was the Pescadores (Magong), and the third was Dàyuan. The VOC considered the first two locations the most advantageous trading posts, while Dàyuan was merely a fallback option to compete with Spain after failing to secure the other two. For the VOC, the Pescadores offered a natural harbor and was part of Ming Dynasty territory, whereas Dàyuan lacked a good harbor, and its population was primarily indigenous peoples. The VOC's military action against Macau was not only a significant event in the East Asian seas but also a pivotal turning point in the transformation of Taiwan.

1.3 Background of Formosa (Taiwan)

Before the 16th century, Taiwan was still a primitive and desolate land with sparse human settlement, and the exact number of inhabitants remains unknown. The main residents were the Austronesian indigenous peoples, along with settlements of pirates, fishermen, and merchants (Dong & Xu, 2022). According to available records, at that time, aside from a small number of Han Chinese, Japanese, and Ryukyuan, the majority of the population comprised indigenous peoples of the Austronesian language family. These indigenous groups were spread across Taiwan, each with its own distinct language, customs, and traditions, forming independent and non-subordinate societies (Zheng, 2004).

Han Chinese and Japanese people primarily resided in the coastal plains of western Taiwan, where Japanese merchants and fishermen established a small village at the entrance to a bay on the southwestern coastline (present-day Anping, Tainan), known as Takasago. They mainly engaged in acquiring deer hides, which were sold to Japan, as Taiwan's deer hides were used by Japanese samurai to craft armor (Wu, 2008). As late as the mid-19th century, Japanese maps and texts alternately referred to Taiwan as Formosa or Takasago (Heyns, 2000).

Taiwan has been known by many names throughout history. In 16th- and 17th-century Western documents, the Portuguese referred to it as “Lequeo Pequeno,” the Spanish as “Ilha Formosa,” “Hermosa,” or “Pakan,” and the Japanese as “Takasago” (also translated as “Takamatsu” or “Takasama”). The West even referred to Taiwan as the land of the “King of Dongning” (東寧王) or “Coxinga.” (國姓爺) Taiwan first appeared on world maps in 1554, when it was marked as ‘Ilha Formosa’ on a map drawn by the Portuguese cartographer Lopo Homem. This map is currently housed in the National Archaeological Museum in Florence, Italy (Liu, 2015).

2. DUTCH ECONOMIC AND TRADE ACTIVITIES IN DÀYUAN

2.1 Early Colonial Period and Friendly Relations with the Indigenous People

The Dutch initially planned to use Macau or the Pescadores as maritime trade hubs to facilitate trade between the Ming Dynasty, Japan, Southeast Asia, and Europe. However, they were expelled by the Portuguese and driven away by the Ming Dynasty's navy. In August 1624, they shifted their focus to Taiwan, establishing a base at Dàyuan. The first governor, Martinus Sonck, set up a simple trading post and Fort Zeelandia (安平古堡) at North Shanhui (北汕尾) (present-day Sicao, Tainan), transforming the settlement into a transit point for VOC trade with the Ming Dynasty and Japan. This also marked the establishment of the first recorded colonial administration in Taiwan's history.

In early January 1625, the Dutch paid 15 pieces of cangan cloth to the Siraya people of Xingang (新港) (now Xinshi District, Tainan) in exchange for all the land around Chihkan (now known as Fort Provintia), establishing it as their political and economic center and as a market town to accommodate merchants engaged in trade (Blusse & Everts, 2000a). During the early stages of colonization, Dutch influence was limited to Dàyuan and surrounding villages, including Xingang, Mados (麻荳) (now Madou District, Tainan), Siaolung (蕭壟) (now Jiayi District, Tainan), Mokuwan (目加溜灣) (now Anding District, Tainan), and Damujiang (大目降) (now Xinhua District, Tainan). Mados was the largest settlement, followed by Siaolung, Xingang, and Mokuwan.

At that time, the Dutch referred to the people of Formosa as the Siraya (西拉雅族人), the indigenous group living in the area. In their efforts to establish trade with the Ming Dynasty, the Dutch maintained friendly relations with the island's inhabitants, including indigenous people, as well as a small number of Chinese, Japanese, and Okinawans. Their goal was not to gain future benefits from the residents, but rather to prevent the inhabitants from becoming adversaries (Cheng, 2000).

2.2 The Introduction of Fujian Minnan People for Land Reclamation

At this time, the Dutch in Dàyuan were in urgent need of labor to develop the land. Unable to persuade the local indigenous people or bring in settlers from Europe, the VOC turned to recruit large numbers of Han Chinese from the Minnan region of Fujian for land reclamation. Beginning in 1590, the Fujian Minnan (福建閩南) region suffered from a series of natural disasters, and the Ming Dynasty's long-standing maritime ban left many coastal inhabitants impoverished. After 1627, a severe drought caused widespread famine, leading to numerous deaths. The survivors became refugees and beggars. In their struggle for survival, people began migrating in large numbers (Antony, 2010).

Zheng Zhilong, with his ships and knowledge of Taiwan's geography, quickly extended a helping hand to the starving population, organizing a large-scale migration of famine-stricken civilians to Taiwan (Lian, n.d.). This marked the first organized migration from the Fujian Minnan region to Taiwan, providing significant support for Koxinga (Zheng Chenggong) in his future efforts to drive out the VOC.

The large influx of Minnan migrants continually poured in, altering Taiwan's demographic structure and giving rise to a multi-ethnic settler and colonial society (Zhuang, 2001). This migration, to some extent, stimulated and transformed the existing ways of life and livelihood patterns. Similar to the European settlers who arrived in North American colonies at the time, these pioneers sought to escape the unbearable conditions in their homeland or were drawn by the prospects of establishing a new home on the frontier.

August 1625 marked a turning point for Zheng Zhilong. The elderly Li Dan passed away while returning to Japan from Taiwan, and his properties and personnel (soldiers) in Taiwan were transferred to his adopted son, Zheng Zhilong, for management. In early 1628, Zheng Zhilong replaced the VOC's most important commercial partner in Xiamen, Xu Xinsu (許心素), making Xiamen a crucial base for Zheng's maritime trade and piracy activities (Antony, 2010). He also became the largest supplier of goods to the Dutch in Dàyuan (Wong, 2017). In September 1628, Zheng Zhilong accepted the summons of Xiong Wenkan (熊文燦), the newly appointed Fujian Governor of the Ming Dynasty. He was granted the title of Guerrilla Shogun and tasked with overseeing coastal security and commanding the troops.

Emerging as a pirate from the Fujian Minnan region, Zheng, with an armed fleet with the finest cannons and advanced military technology from Western maritime powers, posed a significant threat to the already crumbling Ming Dynasty. Given Zheng Zhilong's military strength, maritime trade, and understanding of European powers, the Ming Dynasty had no choice but to offer him a position, hoping to entice him into helping defend the coast and combat the growing smuggling and rampant piracy.

2.3 Zheng Zhilong Engages in Smuggling in an Official Capacity

Although the VOC did not gain direct trade opportunities with the Ming Dynasty, it benefited from re-export trade in Dàyuan by enticing Zheng Zhilong, a pirate-turned-official, and other local officials to cooperate in exchange for high profits. They purchased raw silk, silk, porcelain, and other goods to sell to Japan, Batavia, and even re-export to Europe. Additionally, they sent Southeast Asian spices and goods from Japan and Europe back to Fujian's maritime merchants or Dàyuan traders, profiting from these commercial transactions. During the early period of Dutch colonization in Dàyuan, the VOC's profits were not derived from Taiwan's own socioeconomic development, but from the goods supplied by Zheng Zhilong and other officials, maritime merchants, pirates, and smugglers from Fujian (Wang, & Xie, 2000). This marked the VOC's significant commercial gain from the re-export trade in Dàyuan.

However, by 1641, after the Dutch fell out with Zheng Zhilong, he nearly cut off the supply of goods, leading to a decline in Dàyuan's re-export trade revenue. Profits dropped to about half of their earlier peak. Since the Ming Dynasty prohibited direct trade with Japan, Zheng Zhilong, as a Fujian official, attempted to use Dàyuan as a third-party location, allowing the Dutch to conduct trade with Japan. The Dutch, possibly aware of this arrangement, repeatedly delayed payments to Zheng Zhilong. In 1641, three ships loaded with raw silk, silk, porcelain, and other goods bound for Dàyuan were unable to pay for their cargo because the VOC had used their silver for trade in Coromandel. In anger, Zheng Zhilong ordered these ships to change course and head directly for Japan (Cheng, 2013). This marked the beginning of direct trade between Japan and Zheng Zhilong, bypassing Dàyuan. What had once been a business partnership with the Dutch in Dàyuan turned into fierce commercial rivalry. Zheng Zhilong began sending ships directly from Xiamen to Japan, a shift that deeply impacted VOC profits. In addition to facing competition from Portugal, Spain, and England, the VOC now had to contend with the formidable Zheng Zhilong, who controlled access to Ming Dynasty goods.

2.4 Decline in Maritime Trade Revenue and the Expansion of Local Taxes in Dàyuan

As trade revenue in Dàyuan declined, the Dutch authorities were forced to seek alternative sources of economic income. In 1642, they began collecting annual

tributes from the indigenous tribes of Taiwan to cover the expenses of missionaries, churches, and schools. This also helped ensure the compliance of the indigenous people. This practice continued until 1650, when the Batavia authorities ordered its termination and decided that the VOC would henceforth bear these costs (Kang, 2005).

The revenue in Dàyuan gradually shifted from re-export trade taxes to local taxes. According to the regulations of the VOC colonial government, only "all Han Chinese and indigenous people under our jurisdiction" were required to pay head taxes, while European citizens and the families of employees were exempt. This created a clearly unequal system, with taxes imposed solely on the Han Chinese and indigenous people (Liu, 2011). In 1643, the Batavia authorities instructed the governor of Taiwan to increase tax revenue to support other colonial regions. Consequently, various new taxes were introduced, and in 1644, the new "t Verpachten van Dorpen" (贖社制度; Village franchise system) was implemented to secure higher and more stable tax revenues. Under the Village franchise system, direct trade between Han Chinese and indigenous people was abolished, and the Dutch became the rule-makers and arbiters of trade (Li, 2014).

The 10th Governor, Nicolass Verburgh, described Taiwan as the colony with the highest tax revenue in the VOC's global empire, stating that the Han Chinese were the only bees on the island that produced honey (Minnan are the only bees on Formosa that give honey) (Andrade, 2008). However, the Dutch did not value these "bees" that brought them wealth. Instead, they continued to exploit, oppress, and abuse these hard-working people. The harsh taxation system eventually led to the Gouqua Faet/Faijet incident on September 7, 1652, involving the agricultural landowner Guo Huaiyi, which was recorded in Dutch documents (Zheng, 2011). After the incident was quelled, the VOC did not change the overall tax structure of the colony. Instead, they continued to recruit more Han Chinese from the Fujian Minnan and Guangdong Yuebei regions to develop land, planting sugarcane and rice.

3. THE NETHERLANDS ASSERTS SOVEREIGNTY OVER TAIWAN

3.1 The Hamada Yahyōe Incident

The Hamada Yahyōe (濱田彌兵衛) incident began as a simple commercial tax dispute but gradually evolved into a situation that prompted the Dutch to recognize the importance of asserting sovereignty over Dàyuan, emphasizing that Dàyuan was an inseparable part of the VOC. Before the Dutch fully occupied Dàyuan, there was a settlement called "Takasago Village," which housed about 160 Japanese merchants and fishermen. These individuals purchased deer products from the local indigenous people to sell in Japan and were never required to pay any taxes (Andrade, 2008).

In the early years of Dutch colonization in Dàyuan, the focus was primarily on maritime trade, and the issue of

sovereignty over Dàyuan was not seriously considered. This changed with the Hamada Yahyōe incident, which the Japanese referred to as the "Dàyuan Incident" or "Naichi Incident." This event made the VOC realize that in order to conduct successful trade in Dàyuan and gain a favorable position in trade with both the Ming Dynasty and Japan, they needed to secure the recognition of the local indigenous tribes. As a result, the Dutch shifted their policies towards the indigenous population, beginning to intervene in tribal affairs and engage in military actions against indigenous groups.

In July 1625, the Dutch, seeking to monopolize trade with the Ming Dynasty and Japan, issued a decree prohibiting Ming Chinese merchants residing in Japan from trading in Dàyuan. They also imposed a ten percent tax on goods imported to and exported from Dàyuan. This led to the 1626 incident involving the Japanese Shuinsen (licensed trade ships; Japanese armed merchant vessels). The official trade agent in Nagasaki, Suetsugu Heizō, sent Hamada Yahyōe to Dàyuan to procure goods. However, the Dutch imposed a forced tax on the goods, which resulted in dissatisfaction among the Japanese traders.

At this time, Hamada Yahyōe discovered that the Xingang tribe of indigenous people were also dissatisfied with the Dutch colonizers. He, along with the tribe's elder Dika, traveled to Japan to present their grievances to the governor of Nagasaki. They later presented themselves as a "Takasago delegation" and petitioned the Tokugawa Shogunate for protection in exchange for land. Upon their return to Taiwan, Dika and other indigenous leaders were imprisoned by the Dutch (Chen, 2004).

From Japan's perspective, their previous transactions at Dàyuan were not subject to taxation. However, after the Dutch occupied Taiwan and began imposing taxes, they hindered and detained figures such as Dika (理加), while disregarding the legitimacy of the Shuinsen (Red Seal Ships) that had not been certified by the Tokugawa shogunate. The "Red Seal" (Shuinsen) refers to a trade permit issued by the Japanese government in the late 16th century. Introduced by Toyotomi Hideyoshi, it was designed to control the profits from overseas trade and the acquisition of new technologies, granting legal trade certificates to assert control over foreign commerce. During the Tokugawa shogunate, this policy was adopted and expanded, symbolizing Japan's extension of influence overseas. Offending or obstructing ships holding a Red Seal certificate was considered a direct challenge to Japan (Zheng, 2021).

In June 1628, Hamada Yahyōe, in an effort to rescue Dika and others, forcibly took Pieter Nuyts' eldest son, Laurens Nuyts, along with the interpreter Kallon and others as hostages (Lin, 2008). This incident led Japan to suspend trade with the Dutch, seize Dutch ships, and close the Dutch trading post in Hirado. Dutch officials in Batavia recognized the gravity of the situation and, in order to prevent further deterioration of relations and protect their commercial interests, sent Hans Putmans in June 1629 to replace Nuyts.

Putmans subsequently declared Nuyts guilty, and in March 1630, Nuyts was imprisoned as part of efforts to restore relations with Japan (Zheng, 2002). After a series of diplomatic negotiations, in September 1632, Batavia, seeking to regain Japanese trade privileges and resolve lingering grievances, was compelled to extradite Nuyts to Japan for imprisonment. In 1633, Japan finally allowed the VOC to resume trade in Hirado, and Nuyts was released only in 1636 (Blusse, 2003).

3.2 Military Conquest of Indigenous Peoples for Sovereign Legitimacy

The "Hamada Yahyōe incident" led the VOC to realize that in order to successfully conduct trade, levy taxes, gain economic benefits, and secure a favorable position in trade with the Ming Dynasty and Japan in Dàyuan, it was essential to gain the recognition of the local indigenous tribes. This was necessary to prevent future incidents in which the tribes might seek assistance from Japan. Consequently, the Governor of Batavia issued an order for the officials in Dàyuan to take action in asserting sovereignty over the indigenous tribes on the island, expelling pirates, Japanese pirates, and smugglers engaged in illegal trade, and imposing a tribute tax.

Military Conquests, Between November 1633 and December 1640, there were six military campaigns against Lamey Island (拉美島), including the "Sailing Golden Lion Incident". In 1635, the conquest of the Madou Tribe forced them to sign the "Madou Treaty" on December 18, a treaty of submission to the Dutch. In 1635, the conquest of the Madou Tribe compelled them to sign the "Madou Treaty" on December 18, which recognized Dutch colonial rule. This treaty is currently preserved in the National Archives of The Hague, Netherlands (Jiang, 1999: 22).

After the Dutch military conquest of the Madou tribe, the Madou Treaty altered the Dutch colonizers' policy towards Dàyuan and the surrounding lands. The Dutch began using military actions to intimidate and attack several indigenous tribes in the area. Many tribes, unable to defeat the Dutch in battle and fearing further attacks, signed submission treaties similar to the Madou Treaty, offering land and recognizing the Dutch as their rulers (Zheng, n.d.). This shift changed the way the VOC asserted sovereignty over Dàyuan. On February 20, 1636, the Dutch held a submission ceremony with 28 tribes at the Xinguang tribe. By six months later, the number of tribes that had submitted had increased to 57, marking the Dutch colonization of the entire southwestern region of Taiwan (Blusse, & Everts, 2000b).

What followed was the establishment of colonial dominance, which created institutionalized vassal relationships. The Dutch authorities as lords, while the indigenous people were as vassals. This relationship was maintained through local councils and annual tribute. In name, the indigenous people were protected by the Dutch lords; in practice, however, they were obligated to perform duties as the price of this protection, such as participating in military campaigns, delivering official documents, and

performing other miscellaneous tasks (Weng, 2008). The Dutch also sought to assimilate the indigenous people through Christianity, promoting the recognition of Christ and the Dutch civilizing mission (Lin, 2009). For those tribes that had not been conquered, such as the Dadu King Tribe (大肚王部落), the Langjiao Tribe (琅嶠部落) on the Hengchun Peninsula, the Maja Tribe (瑪家部落), the Makatto Tribe (馬卡道族部落), and the Fangsu Tribe (放索部落), their chieftain autonomy was preserved. During the height of Dutch colonial rule, their jurisdiction was limited to the western plains and did not extend to the entire island of Taiwan.

4. RELIGIOUS CONVERSION AND INTERMARRIAGE TO ASSIMILATE INDIGENOUS PEOPLES

4.1 Educating the Indigenous Peoples Through Christian Doctrine

One of the key policies during the Dutch colonial period in Taiwan was the conversion of indigenous peoples to Christianity. Each time the Dutch military conquered a tribe, they sent missionaries to focus on converting and assimilating the people, encouraging them to adopt Dutch culture and Christianity. The Dutch seamlessly combined military force with religious conversion. On one hand, they used force to subdue the indigenous tribes; on the other, they spread Christian teachings, tightly integrating missionary work, cultural assimilation, and governance. Indigenous peoples within their jurisdiction were required to embrace their religion.

Although in some instances, the Dutch colonial period objectively contributed to the spread of Western civilization and marked the beginning of documented interactions between the Dutch colonizers and the indigenous peoples. However, the colonizers' pursuit of self-interest meant that this process of "civilizing," educating, or converting to Christianity was often accompanied by unequal oppression and enslavement. This clearly had a dehumanizing aspect, with the primary goal being to weaken the indigenous people's resistance to foreign rule, reduce conflicts with the Dutch authorities, and stabilize the colonial order (Masselman, 1961).

The first pastor to arrive in Dàyuan was Georgius Candidius, who reached the area in May 1627. He went to Xingang Tribe, a settlement with good relations with the Dutch, to learn the local language and understand the customs of the Xingang people. Candidius wrote various religious materials in the indigenous language, translating the Bible, Collection of Prayers, and The Truth of Salvation into Xingang, and also published a Xingang dictionary. He used the Xingang language to orally spread Christian teachings (Cha, 2015). The second pastor, Robertus Junius, arrived in 1629. Like Candidius, Junius preached in Xingang. Xingang is a dialect of the Siraya language, which belongs to the

Austronesian language family. It is closely related to the languages of nearby tribes, allowing for mutual intelligibility.

Missionaries used indigenous languages to teach the people about Christ, which not only benefited the colonial government and commercial development but also facilitated the acculturation and deeper assimilation of the local indigenous population, fostering a greater identification with the Dutch. For the indigenous peoples, who did not have their own written language, learning to use the Latin alphabet (also known as the Roman alphabet) for spelling, literacy, record-keeping, and policy implementation aimed to help them recognize the Dutch and embrace the Christian faith (Chang, 2005). This approach not only benefited the Dutch colonial government and commercial interests but also helped transform indigenous tribes into literate, civilized societies.

4.2 Exile of Tribal Shamans

While the missionary work of spreading Christian teachings undoubtedly brought western civilization and enlightenment to the indigenous peoples, it was often accompanied by the colonizers' pursuit of self-interest, leading to brutal massacres, conquest, unequal oppression, and enslavement (Lin, 2008). For example, in order to effectively promote the conversion of indigenous peoples to Christianity within his jurisdiction, Pastor Candidius viewed the tribal shamans as the greatest obstacle to his mission. He forbade the indigenous people from listening to the shamans and sought to diminish their influence. In 1641, the Dutch authorities launched a military campaign that led to the exile of over 250 shamans from various tribes to Zhuluo Mountain (諸羅山) (modern-day Chiayi). They were not permitted to return to their tribes until 1652, and were prohibited from engaging in their original religious practices. However, only 48 shamans survived. This action was not merely aimed at the shamans; to some extent, it was an effort to eradicate what the Dutch considered heretical practices, thus brutally dismantling the tribes' original belief systems (Huang, 2022).

The motivation for driving out or hunting shamans can be traced back to the European Middle Ages, when the belief in "witch hunts" was prevalent. Christianity and Catholicism held that individuals who violated social norms or religious laws were either possessed by demons or witches themselves. This belief persisted into the seventeenth century, during the age of discovery, mercantilism, and global evangelism, including the Dutch colonial period in Dàyuan. At that time, the environment lacked religious tolerance, and individuals were forced to choose between Christianity and Catholicism. As a result, many lost their lives due to differences in religious beliefs and affiliations (Liu, 2020). The Dutch colonial authorities found certain social customs of the tribes incompatible with Christian doctrine, and shamans, whose practices differed from Christian teachings, were brutally exiled and persecuted.

Many indigenous people from various tribes not only rejected Christian teachings but also developed strong feelings of resistance. Under the coercion of Dutch colonial

authorities, many indigenous individuals, in order to avoid failure in hunting or farming, were forced to accept Christianity against their will (Kang, 2005). While it seemed that Christianity changed the traditional beliefs of the indigenous peoples, in reality, it was more a result of the indigenous peoples' compromise with the Dutch colonizers. Specifically, the adoption of Christianity by the Xinguang tribe was largely a pragmatic response to the intense conflicts between tribes (Huang, 2022).

Religion arises from the human spirit; it is a voluntary and spontaneous act, not a forced conversion that fosters affection for the "master" of colonial rule. Religions in different regions or among different ethnic groups each have their own cultural significance, and they spread their doctrines through various methods to offer comfort to their followers. During the age of discovery, mercantilism, and global evangelism, Western religions believed that the indigenous peoples of the conquered colonies must worship their "Lord." As a result, we can easily observe throughout history how the West has waged wars in the name of religion.

Religion is the content of culture, and culture is the form of religion. Without culture, religion cannot express itself (Tillich, 1976). Although culture and religion may appear distinct, they are inseparable. In 1662, when the Ming Dynasty's Zheng Chenggong forces landed in Dàyuan, they were determined to destroy the churches, schools, and religious books that had once caused great suffering, in order to restore their former beliefs and customs. They rejoiced in their liberation from the forced Christianity to which they had been subjected (Shi, 2019).

4.3 Establishing Christian Schools to Assimilate Indigenous People

On May 26, 1636, Taiwan's first religious school was established in the Xinguang tribe, making it one of the earliest regions to introduce Western education. The curriculum not only included Christian doctrine but also adopted the Latin alphabet (also known as "Roman letters") to teach literacy and writing skills (Lee, 2003). Following the success of this school, the Dutch quickly expanded the initiative to the Siraya region (the area between Tainan's Xinshi and Chiayi City) and the Huweilang area (虎尾壟區) (from Huwei Township to Erlin Township), establishing more religious schools. The students were divided into three categories: children, adult men, and women (He, 2017). The goal was to introduce Christian teachings to indigenous students from an early age, enabling them to become devout Christians, obey the Dutch, and, in the process, identify outstanding individuals who could remain in the area to spread the gospel. This approach helped resolve issues such as the shortage of missionaries and language barriers, while also reducing the costs of hiring European missionaries for the VOC (Shi, 2019).

In the early stages, education took an indigenization approach, using the indigenous people's native language as a tool to spread religious doctrine. However, by the mid-

colonial period, as missionaries familiar with indigenous languages gradually left Dàyuan, the Dutch colonial authorities became reluctant to spend heavily on increasing the number of clergy. Additionally, the unique climate of Dàyuan often caused missionaries to contract diseases and die. In 1648, Dutch language education was introduced, modeled after Dutch schools, with classes held for two hours in the morning and two hours in the afternoon. However, due to a lack of consensus, Dutch language education was not widely implemented. There were two main sources for school teachers: soldiers from the military and the indigenous people themselves. Indigenous teachers were selected from among the outstanding students at the school (Lin, 2009). Sending soldiers to teach required less financial support, while indigenous teachers were required by the VOC to adopt Dutch names and wear Dutch clothing (Kang, 2005).

From the perspective of human civilization, writing serves as the carrier of culture, and historical standards are recorded through text. Those who control written language often view themselves as the rational party, believing they have an obligation to help those without civilization—who are seen as barbaric and primitive—transition toward a more civilized way of life and understanding. Education is the most effective means to achieve this, as it enables indigenous people to adopt the colonizers' perspective. This process involves the dynamics of "power/knowledge" and "transplant/recognition" (Foucault, 1980). The sources of power are diverse, encompassing both external forces and internal influences that shape thought. True power functions as a network, deeply embedded in every corner of the individual's mind, achieving the greatest effect with the least cost (Yang, 1999). Furthermore, discipline is one of the sources of power relations. Foucault argues that moral instruction acts as a disciplinary mechanism capable of generating subtle coercion within learners' minds, restricting their worldview and actions (Danaher et al., 2000). Therefore, the education and civilizing efforts implemented by the Dutch on the inhabitants indeed had a submissive effect.

4.4 Assimilating Indigenous People Through Intermarriage

In Taiwan, the Dutch and their European employees were predominantly male, with fewer females. The Dutch authorities in Batavia supported and encouraged them to marry local women who had already converted to Christianity. This was because they observed a significant number of tribe members converting to Christianity, and from their observations during the Portuguese colonial period in Ambon, they noted that children of mixed European heritage were highly loyal to the colonial authorities. Intermarriage was seen as a means of enhancing the security of the colonizers (Chiu, 2008).

Intermarriage became a key part of the Dutch strategy to gain the recognition and support of the indigenous peoples in Taiwan. First, it symbolized the strengthening of interactions between the Dutch and indigenous groups, fostering greater

social integration. Second, it helped to establish a rich network of social resources for the Dutch colonizers, allowing them to gain more support from local tribes (Borao, 2009). Third, intermarriage facilitated further psychological integration between the two groups, reducing the psychological distance created by the colonial system, decreasing perceived rejection, and significantly increasing recognition of the colonizers (Koelet, van Mol, & de Valk, 2016).

Milton Gordon, in his study of ethnic integration in the United States, systematically divides the process of assimilation into seven dimensions: (1) cultural or behavioral assimilation (Acculturation); (2) integration or merging of social structures (Structural assimilation); (3) intergroup intermarriage (Amalgamation); (4) merging of group consciousness or identity (Identification assimilation); (5) the elimination of group prejudice in consciousness (Absence of prejudice); (6) the elimination of discriminatory behaviors in areas such as economics, employment, and education (Absence of discrimination); and (7) integration in public affairs (Civic assimilation) (Gordon, 1964). Joseph Beal Steere has described the history of Dutch missionary work in Taiwan, where he emphasized the colonizers' victory and the superiority of Christianity. He suggested that Christianity could transcend previously unequal social classes, allowing colonial rulers at the top to intermarry with the indigenous people, who were considered lower in status. This intermarriage, facilitated by Christianity, brought the two races closer together (Lin, 2009).

In 2002, Jiang pointed out that even though indigenous people converted to Christianity and intermarried with the Dutch, only a small number were accepted into Dutch society. The majority were still required to remain in their original tribes and comply with the many restrictions imposed by the Dutch. For the Dutch colonizers, intermarriage was one of the means used to legitimize their rule in Taiwan. According to social identity theory, social identity is composed of three basic processes: categorization, identification, and comparison. Through interpersonal interactions, individuals acquire specific social identities, and based on these roles, they form self-concepts, leading to the development of their identity (Hogg, Meehan, & Farquharson, 2010). Identity is a psychological state that involves complex cognitive processes. While the relationship between intergroup marriage and social integration is not absolute, it is primarily shaped by the complexity of racial and religious issues (Song, 2009).

In 2002, Zheng analyzes the research of Pol Heyns, who examined the Dutch marriage registers from 1650 to 1661. He found no records of marriages between Han Chinese and local tribal women. This was because the Dutch authorities imposed a barrier on such unions, stipulating that only Christians or those who had received Christian education could marry local women. Those who had previously married were required to separate unless the Han Chinese spouse was

baptized and converted. By 1661, the Dutch East India Company had stationed over 2,000 male personnel in Taiwan. Analyzing the birthplaces listed in the marriage registers, it is estimated that the number of Dutch descendants born in Taiwan exceeded 700, including a significant proportion of mixed-race offspring born to Dutch or European employees. However, there are very few relevant records. It is unquestionable that Dutch descendants, or those of other European countries, were present in the indigenous tribes of Taiwan (Han, 2005).

5. THE DUTCH LOST THEIR SOVEREIGNTY OVER TAIWAN

5.1 Zheng Chenggong's Eastern Expedition to Taiwan

Under Dutch colonial rule, Taiwan can be considered a place completely unaffected by China's feudal society. The decision by Zheng Chenggong to launch an eastern campaign to expel the Dutch from Taiwan is explored by Patrizia Carioti in her book *Koxinga: The Prominent Figure on the International Stage of the Far East*. In this work, Carioti examines the major events that occurred during the 1630s and 1640s, which had a significant impact on the Far Eastern seas, and the economic perspectives that these events sparked (Zhuang, Su, & Nie, 1996). Carioti argues that:

Firstly, the VOC and Zheng's maritime trade (under Zheng Zhilong) were initially marked by conflicting interests, which gradually developed into inevitable competition and confrontation. Secondly, Zheng's maritime trade accounted for about 80% of Japan's total maritime market, while the Dutch were the only European operators in Japan at the time. In addition to Zheng's trade, there were many other maritime traders. To defeat these traders, the Dutch exploited the conflicts between them, employing a strategy of sowing discord and isolating each one to maximize their commercial interests. Thirdly, after Zheng Chenggong's failed northern campaign to Nanjing and the advancing Qing forces, along with the Dutch use of Dàyuan (modern-day Taiwan) as their base, the Dutch posed a significant long-term threat to the survival and development of Zheng's maritime trade.

Therefore, expelling the Dutch from Taiwan and using the island as a base for continuing overseas trade and resisting the Qing became a crucial decision for the survival of Zheng Chenggong and his Zheng family maritime traders. The eastern campaign to Taiwan was not merely a strategic military retreat; it was, in fact, a move to establish Taiwan as a new starting point (Nie, 1998). In March 1661, Zheng Chenggong assembled 400 ships and approximately 25,000 soldiers at Liaoluo Bay in Kinmen (金門料羅灣). Of these, around 16,000 were combat-ready, well-equipped, and highly trained soldiers—ten times the number of Dutch soldiers (Wong, 2017). The total number of soldiers even exceeded the entire Dutch forces across Asia. After landing, several thousand Han Chinese residents voluntarily went to the shore to assist in guiding Zheng Chenggong's forces ashore and

participated in the siege of the Dutch at Dàyuan (Andrade, 2013).

The Dutch, with only about 1,200 soldiers, held out at Fort Zeelandia for nine months (from May 1661 to January 1662). After waiting in vain for reinforcements and facing certain defeat, Governor Coyett proposed terms for negotiation with Zheng Chenggong: first, Zheng Chenggong would withdraw his troops, and the Dutch would compensate him for all costs; or second, the Dutch would surrender all of Formosa to Zheng Chenggong's rule, retaining only Dàyuan (modern-day Anping, Tainan) and the fort there as a trading post (Xu, 2014). At the time, Coyett believed that Zheng Chenggong would accept the second option in order to avoid a confrontation with the VOC. However, Zheng Chenggong insisted on the complete withdrawal of the Dutch from Formosa, thereby ending the Dutch colonial rule in Taiwan, which had lasted for thirty-eight years (1624-1662) (Wong, 2017). The "Dutch Surrender Document" from the Zheng-Dutch War is preserved in the National Archives of The Hague.

5.2 The Dutch Loss of Formosa by Coyett

In 1675, *Neglected Formosa* was published in Amsterdam. The book recounts the story of Frederik Coyett, the last Dutch governor of Dàyuan, who, after leading his troops back to Batavia, was prosecuted for the loss of Taiwan. He was sentenced to death, had his property confiscated, and was stripped of all honors and reputation. After spending two years in prison, his sentence was commuted to life imprisonment on the island of Banda in the East Indies, specifically on Ay Island, where he endured eight years in exile. It was only through the efforts of his friends and family that he eventually received a pardon from the Prince of Orange, the ruler of the Dutch Republic at the time.

Before returning to the Dutch, Frederik Coyett, with a sense of personal honor, wrote a stern account of the reasons for the loss of Taiwan, taking full responsibility for the failure and providing a strong defense for himself. His writings serve as a valuable historical record of the pivotal battle that determined Taiwan's fate. In the book, he accuses the Batavia authorities of despotism and incompetence. He claims that, despite knowing Zheng Chenggong would attempt to take Taiwan following his failed northern campaign to Nanjing, the Batavia authorities, hindered by complacency and personal grudges, missed the opportunity to act. This allowed Zheng Chenggong to expand his influence, and ultimately, the Dutch had no choice but to abandon the fort and surrender. Although they lost Taiwan, they did not view it as a failure of duty (Campbell, & Lin, 2011).

Coyett summarized the two main reasons for the loss of Taiwan as follows:

First, as early as 1646, the VOC had already learned through various channels that Zheng Zhilong had surrendered to the Qing, the King of Tang had been killed, and Zheng Chenggong had raised an army to resist the Qing and planned to march north to Nanjing. However, the Batavia

headquarters mistakenly believed that their naval strength was sufficient to deter Zheng Chenggong from openly challenging them. As the situation in the Southern Ming grew unstable, Governor Frederik Coyett repeatedly reported and predicted that Zheng Chenggong would inevitably focus on overseas expansion and attack the nearby Taiwan. Coyett believed that, since Zheng Chenggong was unlikely to defeat the Qing forces in land battles, he would turn his attention to attacking other territories, ultimately jeopardizing the VOC's position in Taiwan. Coyett repeatedly requested reinforcements from headquarters, but these requests were ignored and delayed until 1661, when Zheng Chenggong crossed the sea to launch his attack, and the nightmare finally became a reality.

Second, the incompetence of the Batavia authorities: Although they had long been aware of the threat posed by Zheng Chenggong to Taiwan, they were unwilling to allocate funds and resources for defense, which was the primary reason for the loss of Taiwan. The previous Dutch Governor of Taiwan, Nicholas Verburgh (1649-1653), had repeatedly misled the company's senior leadership, mocking the current governor, Coyett, for his cowardice and fear of battle. In a critical situation, on September 20, 1660, Batavia sent an expeditionary fleet to Dàyuan with only 12 ships and 600 soldiers. The commander, Jan van der Laan, was a stubborn and foolish man who mistakenly believed the rumors that Zheng Chenggong was not preparing to attack. After arriving in Dàyuan, he repeatedly clashed with local officials and insisted on attacking Macau to recover military expenses (Campbell, 2011). The following year, on February 27, 1661, he took almost all the ships and military officers stationed in Taiwan with him when he sailed away, leaving only two ships to return to Batavia, a small communication boat, a flat-bottomed boat, two captains, and more than 1,200 soldiers without any other officers to defend Taiwan. This left Taiwan vulnerable, allowing Zheng Chenggong to launch his expulsion campaign without restraint (Yang, 2000).

If we view the threat posed by Zheng Chenggong as an external force contributing to the Dutch failure, then during the Dutch colonial period, a large number of Han Chinese were brought in from Fujian and southern Fujian. Following the 'Hamada Yahyōe' incident, the Dutch imposed colonial sovereignty over indigenous tribes through military means, instituting systems such as the village franchise system, taxation, and the forced conversion of residents to Christianity. These actions led to widespread discontent and uprisings, which became crucial internal factors in determining the outcome of this struggle.

The Minnan people who arrived in Taiwan earlier, within the context of the entire Dutch colonial period, not only provided an invaluable internal ally for Koxinga but also embodied the internal contradictions, dilemmas, and the oppression of both the Han people and the indigenous population by the colonial rulers. This illustrates that high-pressure rule can only temporarily force local people into

submission. It is always bound to involve issues of power, interests, exploitation, and eventual rebellion by the people, a process that sees the constant interchange of positions. Violent conquest inevitably faces both internal contradictions and external challenges, and these injustices toward the people will continue to unfold throughout history.

6. CONCLUSION

An analysis of the nature and scope of Dutch and Spanish colonial rule in Taiwan reveals that it primarily involved colonial policies, economics, religion, education, marriage, and the imposition and assimilation of ideological beliefs. The colonizers controlled resources that allowed them to dominate political and economic structures, and in this environment, the indigenous people of Taiwan were subjugated. The Dutch colonizers, equipped with military power and weapons, employed various forms of hegemony. In addition to using military force to suppress resistance and exploiting conflicts between different tribes, they also utilized softer methods such as religious education, intermarriage, and strategies of integration. This approach stemmed from the observation that those who embraced religious education or intermarried tended to show greater loyalty to the colonial authorities. These methods were not isolated but were closely tied to the colonial economy, religious education, and marriage, enabling the colonizers' culture to infiltrate the lives of the colonized. This process of transformation led the colonized people to identify with their colonizers, resulting in a fate from which they could not escape.

Based on the above statement and analysis, it can be concluded that Macau was the top choice for the VOC, followed by Penghu and, subsequently, Dàyuan. The first two locations were the VOC's primary trade points, and its two invasions of Penghu Island aimed to turn it into 'Macau's second.' However, the Dutch were unable to capture Penghu Island due to the naval power of the Ming Dynasty behind it. The Dutch colonial rule in Taiwan, which lasted for 38 years (1624–1662), was a significant and unique period in Taiwan's history, with the following implications for Taiwan and its indigenous peoples at the time:

Before Dutch Colonization: Taiwan first appeared on world maps in 1554, marked as an island called Ilha Formosa on a world map created by the Portuguese cartographer Lopo Homem. This map is currently housed in the Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Firenze in Italy. Throughout history, Taiwan has been recorded under many different names. In 16th and 17th-century foreign documents, the Portuguese referred to it as "Lequeo Pequeno" (Little Liuqiu), the Spanish called it "Ilha Formosa," "Hermosa," or "Pakan," and the Japanese referred to it as "Takasago" (also translated as "Takasama" or "High Mountain"). At times, Taiwan was also referred to by names such as the "Kingdom of Dongning" or "Coxinga's Taiwan" (referring to Zheng Chenggong, also known as Koxinga).

During Dutch Colonization: For the first time in Taiwan's history, a Western modern nation established military and religious colonial rule over the island. It is evident that all their actions were primarily driven by economic interests, employing strategies such as "using barbarians to control barbarians" and "attacking barbarians with barbarians," alongside efforts in conquest, education, and cultural assimilation. Secondly, the "Hamada Yahyōe" incident led the Dutch to place greater emphasis on asserting their sovereignty over Taiwan. The VOC realized that both military and religious power were necessary to force indigenous tribes to recognize the legitimacy of their colonial rule. Additionally, they implemented a tax system to communicate their control over Taiwan to the local population and foreign nations. Thirdly, the onset of Sinicization in Taiwan occurred because the Dutch were unable to convince the indigenous people to adopt agriculture or to bring in European settlers. Consequently, they turned to large-scale migration from the Minnan region, which marked the beginning of the Sinicization process. During this time, Zheng Zhilong, known as the "King of the Sea," "Pirate King," and a Ming Dynasty official, played a significant role.

Dutch Assimilation of the Indigenous People: The so-called religious indoctrination policy involved missionaries teaching in the local dialects and instructing the indigenous people in the Latin alphabet for spelling and pronunciation. This was considered the first step in the indigenous people's transition to the civilized world. Secondly, the Dutch established religious schools to instill a sense of Dutch identity and Christianity in the next generation of residents. These schools taught the indigenous students literacy, the principles of Christianity, and faith, transforming them into obedient subjects. Through the "salvation" of religion, this subtly established a form of legal authority. Thirdly, the Dutch and other Western personnel in Taiwan encouraged intermarriage with indigenous people who had been baptized as Christians. This was because they observed that mixed-race children born during the Portuguese colonial period in Amboina exhibited strong loyalty to the colonial authorities. Intermarriage was seen as a strategy to enhance the security of the colonizers. Fourthly, the Dutch coerced the indigenous people into converting to Christianity, offering them relative safety and the opportunity to transcend barriers of race, skin color, culture, and economics. Those who did not convert to Christianity were viewed as outsiders and were at risk of extermination.

When the Dutch Lost Taiwan: The internal contradictions of the VOC, along with ignored geopolitical factors, made maritime trade the main means of survival for Zheng Chenggong. Due to Zheng Chenggong's inability to reverse the Manchu conquest and restore the deposed Ming Dynasty, his expedition to Taiwan temporarily resolved many internal issues within the Zheng family group. Additionally, the large-scale importation of Han Chinese from southern

Fujian during the Dutch colonial period became a key internal factor influencing the outcome of this conflict.

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